

ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the importance of digital transformation in the development of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has the opportunity to demonstrate its enormous potential for pilgrimage tourism more widely by using the most modern digital technologies and international experience. By eliminating existing problems in the field, it is planned to provide pilgrims of the 21st century with new, high-quality and diverse services based on modern digital technologies (mobile apps, AI, AR/VR technologies, virtual guides, etc.). Based on the analysis, an action strategy and practical recommendations were given to increase the attractiveness of pilgrimage tourism, increase the flow of pilgrims, and improve the types and quality of services.*

Keywords: *Digital transformation, pilgrimage tourism, AI algorithms, AR/VR technologies, online booking systems, online payment systems, digital content, virtual guide, “Accidental pilgrimage”, “Multiplier effect”, Humanoid Robotics, Smart APPs for Halal journeys, Accessible Tourism, The modern female traveler.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda ziyorat turizmini yanada rivojlantirishda raqamli transformatsiyaning ta'siri qay darajada muhim ekanligi o'rganadi. O'zbekiston o'zidagi ulkan ziyorat turizmi potensialini eng zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar va xalqaro tajribani qo'llagan holatda yanada kengroq namoyish eta olish imkoniga ega. Sohada mavjud muammolarni bartaraf etish orqali XXI asr ziyoratchilariga zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalarga asoslangan (mobil ilovalar, SI, AR/VR texnologiyalar, virtual gid va boshqalar) yangi, sifatli hamda turfa xizmatlarni taqdim etish ko'zda tutilgan. Tahlillar asosida ziyorat turizmini jozibadorligi oshirish,*

ziyoratchilar oqimini ko'paytirish, xizmat turlari va sifatini oshirish bo'yicha harakatlar strategiyasi va amaliy tavsiyalar berib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *Raqamli transformatsiya, ziyorat turizmi, Sun'iy intellekt algoritmlari, AR/VR texnologiyalar, onlayn bron qilish tizimlari, onlayn to'lov tizimlari, raqamli kontent, virtual gid, “Acidental pilgrimage”, “Multiplikator effekti”, Humanoid Robotics, Smart APPs for Halal journeys, Accessible Tourism, The modern female traveler.*

Introduction

The global digital transformation is one of the key drivers of the gradual growth of global economic indicators. This is particularly noticeable in tourism, especially pilgrimage tourism. The latest technological advances, including artificial intelligence, augmented and virtual reality, virtual guide services, and online booking and payment systems, are fundamentally changing the very concept of pilgrimage. Today, countries such as Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, Turkey, and Qatar, leaders in pilgrimage tourism, are rapidly implementing digital technologies in their tourism sector and achieving annual increases in pilgrimage numbers.

The introduction of digital technologies in tourism has also been elevated to the level of state policy in Uzbekistan. Specifically, the launch of a new National Unified Tourism Platform and its mobile app has been identified as a priority for the digitalization of country's tourism sector[1]. Using this platform, pilgrims can fill out the declaration on line, obtain a tourist electronic SIM card, register at their temporary residence, create an individual convenient tourist itinerary, book or purchase tickets for all modes of transportation online, purchase entrance tickets to all tourist sites online, use a digital guide service that stores all information about the pilgrimage site, and more.

Despite the high potential of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan and the extensive opportunities provided by the state in this area, a number of shortcomings remain. The main challenge in the area of digitalization is the lack of digital content. It is important to highlight the absence of a unified digital registry that fully covers pilgrimage sites, the shortage of a digital guide service providing reliable information on each pilgrimage site, and the deficit of mobile apps. While virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR) technologies are becoming a trend at pilgrimage sites worldwide, it is not always possible to obtain information or make payments using a simple QR code at our pilgrimage sites.

The widespread adoption of digital technologies in pilgrimage tourism will create greater convenience for pilgrims, unlock existing potential through modern technologies, utilize resources efficiently and effectively, and increase the quantity and quality of services. Therefore, studying the trends in the digital transformation of pilgrimage tourism is a pressing scientific and practical challenge today.

Literature review of the topic

As modern information technologies develop, their impact on the tourism industry is growing. Particularly in pilgrimage tourism, which aims to satisfy spiritual needs, the role of digital technologies and the unique experiences they provide pilgrims is extremely important. In this article, we will examine pilgrimage tourism, its impact on the economy, and the role of digital transformation as a factor in the development of pilgrimage tourism. Numerous studies are being conducted worldwide in all these areas.

Let's first consider the concept of pilgrimage tourism, the conceptual foundations of which were developed by D. Timothy and D. Olsen (2006). Charles K. Mann (2011) proposed a theory about why pilgrimage tourism sites attract pilgrims.

L. Budovich (2023) divides pilgrims into groups and examines the socioeconomic impact of each group on the host country. J. Digance (2003) explains that any tourist can become a pilgrim, based on his theory of "Accidental pilgrimage."

B. Vukonic (1996) conducted an in-depth study of the economic impact of pilgrimage tourism, and T. Kozak (2018) detailed the "multiplier effect" in pilgrimage tourism in his research.

A. Berdiev and J. Uzakov (2025) conducted a scientific study of the factors driving the development of pilgrimage tourism in the context of digital transformation, and P. Zaragoza-Saez, B. Marco-Lahara, and M. Ubeda-García (2021) examined the role of tourism industry workers' digital skills in the development of pilgrimage tourism.

In their study, S. Sharma and M.R. Behera (2025) detailed the work being undertaken by leading global pilgrimage tourism centers in the process of digital transformation and the results they achieved. Furthermore, numerous economic, statistical, and legislative sources were used in preparing the article.

Based on the above studies, it can be emphasized that the digital transformation process will enhance the attractiveness of pilgrimage tourism and further increase the flow of modern pilgrims, thereby having a positive impact on our country's economy and the socio-spiritual life of our people. Adapting the global community's experience in digitalizing pilgrimage tourism to Uzbekistan can serve as both a theoretical and practical basis for creating sustainable development strategies in the regions, as well as developing new attractive routes and services through the effective use of digital technologies.

Research methodology

The methodological basis of this study is a comprehensive analytical approach. Several complementary methods were used to comprehensively assess the level of digitalization of pilgrimage tourism sites. First, a theoretical framework was established through a study of existing scientific sources. This was followed by a review of official economic and social statistics, a comparative analysis, and a trend analysis. The results were illustrated using graphical visualization techniques. A tracking analysis of digital content was also conducted to determine the level of digital transformation in the industry. TOWS analysis was used to assess the potential and strategic development directions of pilgrimage tourism sites, analyzing the interrelationships between internal and external factors.

Pilgrimage has long been one of humanity's most enduring spiritual and practical pursuits. At its core are the search for holiness, the pursuit of spiritual truth, or spiritual purification. According to D. Timothy and D. Olsen, "Pilgrimage is understood as a spiritual process that, unlike ordinary travel, separates a person from the realm of everyday life and leads them to sacred places of historical and spiritual significance"[2].

At the same time, the centers of world religions have always attracted pilgrims. The Vatican, Mecca, Jerusalem, Bodh Gaya (the site where Buddha attained enlightenment), and Cahokia (a religious center for the Native American population near St. Louis) are striking examples. These places have always attracted pilgrims from afar. This suggests that the human desire to see sacred places and experience them with one's own eyes has been the root of many civilizations[9].

Today, pilgrimage is an integral part of the global tourism industry. Pilgrimage tourism has its own unique characteristics, including stability, non-seasonal nature, typically being carried out by an organized group, and an emphasis on the spiritual rather than material needs of the pilgrim. Furthermore, statistics show that pilgrims spend several times more than regular tourists. Given these and other factors, pilgrimage tourism can become a strategically important industry for any country.

Pilgrims visiting any country can be roughly divided into two groups:

1. Tourists who come solely for the purpose of pilgrimage;
2. Tourists who, in addition to pilgrimage, also pursue other goals[4].

For people in the first group, the primary goal is to complete all pilgrimage activities at the intended pilgrimage site. For example, the first group of pilgrims includes those performing Hajj or Umrah. The second group knows that their destination has a pilgrimage site and plans to visit it, in addition to other plans (trading, vacationing, medical treatment, etc.). For example, a Muslim visiting Samarkand for the first time definitely plans to visit the Imam al-Bukhari complex. But there is another characteristic of pilgrimage tourism – "accidental pilgrimage"[5]. By definition, a tourist arriving for any purpose other than pilgrimage accidentally learns about a pilgrimage site and visits it. Thus, this tourist, regardless of their primary purpose, becomes a

pilgrim. This is precisely the strength of pilgrimage tourism. Any person coming to our country can be converted into a pilgrim by applying the right marketing strategy.

If we divide tourists visiting our country by purpose of visit, the highest percentage (an average of 84.2%) is among those visiting relatives. By effectively targeting this segment, we can increase the overall number of pilgrims. The second group (an average of 11.07) consists of people coming for tourism purposes. They are expected to visit one or another pilgrimage site during their visit. Pilgrimage sites are located on virtually every tourist route in Uzbekistan. These conclusions are based on statistical data for 2019-2024. It should be emphasized that the very low figures in 2020 and 2021 are the result of the negative impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. From 2022 to the present, all tourism indicators have gradually increased.

Figure 1. Segmentation of tourists visiting Uzbekistan by purpose of visit (2019-2024)¹

The positive impact of pilgrimage tourism on the economy manifests itself in various ways. An increased influx of new pilgrims to a region directly impacts the creation of new jobs, the activation of small businesses related to pilgrimage tourism, the expansion of the market for pilgrimage services, the development of pilgrimage site infrastructure, the attraction of significant foreign and domestic investment, and increased tax revenues from entities operating in this sector. This, in turn, leads to economic development, increased employment and financial potential, improved overall urban infrastructure, enhanced international reputation, and the creation of a positive image that attracts international investment.

Pilgrimage tourism creates a "multiplier effect" in the national economy. Every dollar spent by a pilgrim during their visit generates additional income in related sectors, directly or indirectly linked to tourism. Furthermore, pilgrims who come for pilgrimage tourism spend more than other tourists. This is usually explained by the fact that the pilgrim's religious motives outweigh the economic considerations of the average tourist[3]. According to research by Thomas Kozak, the multiplier effect coefficient for pilgrimage tourism ranges from 2.59 to 4.4. In this case, the money spent by pilgrims simultaneously impacts the service sector, trade, manufacturing, and agriculture[6]. This demonstrates the importance of each pilgrim to the national economy.

¹ www.stat.uz

While pilgrimage tourism has a significant positive impact on the national economy, it can also have negative consequences. First and foremost, it can artificially inflate pilgrimage-related expenses for the pilgrims themselves. In turn, rising prices in developed pilgrimage regions also negatively impact the family budgets of local residents. This includes disruption to the local population's traditional way of life, the potential for negative spiritual influence among representatives of different cultures, and the emergence of an imbalance in the development of

regions with and without tourism potential. Failure by the host government to take the necessary measures can lead to problems similar to those listed above. The positive economic impacts of pilgrimage tourism are presented in the table below. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. The impact of pilgrimage tourism on the economy

Today, when digitalization of all sectors of the global economy is a critical task, pilgrimage tourism is keeping pace with this trend. Today, 69% of purchases in the global tourism market are made through online booking systems[10]. Over 70% of international tourists regularly use one or another mobile app during their travels[7]. With the development of modern digital technologies, the very concept of pilgrimage, as well as the lifestyle and preferences of pilgrims, is changing.

Successful digital transformation will benefit all actors involved in pilgrimage tourism equally. This will benefit both pilgrimage tourism organizers and other tourism industry stakeholders, pilgrims themselves, and related industries. We present more detailed information on this below (Table 1).

The following digital transformation trends are currently observed in the global Islamic pilgrimage tourism market.

1. Humanoid robotics – hybrid robotic systems in pilgrimage tourism. This field, which has experienced rapid development during the COVID-19 pandemic, offers pilgrims robotic services programmed using artificial intelligence. These technologies perform everything from simple mechanical movements to complex services. The main advantage is minimizing human contact, which improves the quality and speed of service. Loading a database of religious or pilgrimage sites into such robotic tools makes service more inclusive.

2. Smart apps for halal travel. Modern pilgrims expect to quickly and easily receive necessary information through mobile apps during their travels, easily plan trips, conveniently perform prayers, and gain new experiences and emotions thanks to technologies such as VR.

3. Accessible tourism. This approach allows for the wider use of digital technologies for inclusive tourism participants. It aims to address the inconveniences experienced by people with disabilities, small children, and the elderly during pilgrimage.

4. The modern female traveler. Recently, the share of women-only groups or individual pilgrims in the pilgrimage tourism market has increased. Providing women-focused services has become a priority for this growing segment. Digital technologies are widely used to provide comfortable, safe, and inclusive services for women[11].

Table-3. The impact of digital transformation on pilgrimage tourism entities

Pilgrimage tourism organizers	Tourism infrastructure entities	Pilgrims	Representatives of related economic sectors
Automation of services (e-visa, electronic queue, online booking systems)	Online monitoring of hotel occupancy (online booking systems)	Easy pilgrimage planning (online platforms, smart apps, navigators, online guides)	An online market for handicrafts and souvenirs is emerging
Monitoring the quality and safety of services	Planning the flow and type of transport	Ease of information search (Sights along the route, 360-degree video content, AR and VR content, digital guide service)	Trade turnover in cashless payment systems is growing
More efficient resource management (online monitoring, tracking, big data)	Systematic dissemination of information about the pilgrimage (in digital format)	Convenience of payment (mobile payment, electronic service)	Demand for IT services will grow. New projects and startups.
Effective digital marketing strategies (digital advertising, targeting, e-WoM)	Quick analysis of requests and service quality	Eliminating language barriers (artificial intelligence, online translators)	The guiding, transport, and other services sectors are undergoing digitalization, with specialized platforms being created.

Conclusions and proposals.

Despite the high potential of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan, systematic efforts to improve the existing infrastructure are needed. We present a series of analytical proposals for the successful digital transformation of pilgrimage tourism.

1. Create a unified digital registry of all pilgrimage sites in our country on a dedicated online platform. To this end, a dedicated group of historians, archaeologists, religious scholars, architects, ethnographers, epigraphists, and other specialists should be formed and provided with all possible practical assistance. They should be tasked, first and foremost, with classifying all pilgrimage sites in our country according to their sacred and non-sacred nature. In this regard, it is necessary to separate symbolic sites from the original pilgrimage sites, as well as sites that have no historical or scientific basis.

2. Based on the collected reliable data, IT specialists should create a platform and its mobile application specifically for pilgrimage tourism and supplement it with digital content;

3. Pilgrimage tourism routes should be strictly segmented, as should the sites along them. Resources currently considered general pilgrimage tourism sites should be divided into more specific areas. Let's consider this using the example of Islamic pilgrimage tourism sites:

- In terms of Islamic architecture: mosques, madrassas, minaret, khanaka, etc.;
- In terms of Islamic sciences: muhaddiths (Imam al-Bukhari, Imam at-Termizi), jurists (Abu Lays Samarkandi, Kaffali Shashi), theologians (Imam Moturudi, Imam Nasafi), Sufi scholars (Baha al-Din Naqshband, Zangi Ota), etc.;

- By specific route or school: School of Tariqa Suhrawardi (Sheikh Zayniddin - Tashkent), (Sheikh Nuriddin Basir - Samarkand), (Sheikh Burkhoniddin Sogardzhi - Samarkand), (Sheikh Shamsiddin Kulol - Shakhrisabz), etc.

This allows each pilgrim to create an individual route in the direction they need.

4. Each pilgrimage site must be displayed on an online map. It must also have a brief description, a 360-degree panoramic video, and links to other related sites within the pilgrimage tourism theme.

5. Each pilgrimage site, if it requires an entrance fee, must have payment options via QR code or NFC.

6. At each pilgrimage site, visitors must be able to obtain reliable and complete information via QR code, digitally, or as a 3D animation, such as in the Nazzar app.

7. Hold a national competition for digital content created using AI about pilgrimage sites and the individuals associated with them, their lives, and their work. This will help increase youth interest in artificial intelligence and digital technologies, as well as select the best ideas and develop them in AR and VR.

8. Support creative and modern technological approaches to demonstrating Uzbekistan's pilgrimage tourism potential to the world. Provide more interesting information about our pilgrimage tourism sites on official and unofficial social media.

9. Develop a unified strategy for promoting Uzbekistan's pilgrimage tourism globally. Widely promote existing national brands of Uzbekistan in the pilgrimage tourism market (Bukhara – "7 Pir," Samarkand – "Imam al-Bukhari," etc.). Also develop new pilgrimage tourism brands (Yassavi Tashkent).

10. When implementing the above recommendations, it is necessary to effectively use the global experience applied at the Center for Islamic Civilization in Tashkent and the Imam al-Bukhari complex in Samarkand.

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